

Technological Assessment of Grape Varieties during the Storage Period

Saimnazarov Yuldash Bekmirzayevich

Doctor of biological science, professor. Rice Research Institute

Mirzakhidov Bakhtiyor Djaliddinovich

Doctor of agricultural sciences., senior researcher. Scientific research institute of horticulture, viticulture and winemaking named after Academician Mahmud Mirzayev

Abduramanova Salamat Khudaybergenovna

Doctor of agricultural sciences., senior researcher. Tashkent State Agrarian University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 June 2024; **Accepted:** 4 July 2024; **Published:** 24 Aug 2024

Abstract: The article presents the data on the technological assessment of grapes during the storage period. The research was carried out at the experimental base of the Samarkand scientific-experimental station of the Research Institute of HVW named after academician M. Mirzayev on the topic “Creation of large-berry and seedless grape varieties in the conditions of Uzbekistan”. The storage of grapes was studied by three common methods: “chiya” (reed braids), “otan” and “zang” on the varieties white Kishmish standard, Kishmish Botir, Kishmish Khishrau and Khusayny standard, Khusayny Muskat and Taify pink.

Keywords: grapes, storage, variety, “chipta”, “otan”, “zang”, braids, temperature, humidity, raisins, berries, cluster, technology.

Introduction: Fresh grapes are rich in valuable nutrients, such as sugar, acids, vitamins, bioactive and mineral substances. Therefore, it is very important not only to increase its production, but also to supply the population with them throughout the winter. Proper storage of grapes helps to obtain additional profits.

For long and qualitative storage of grapes it is required to choose table-grape varieties in the late ripening periods: Oktyabrsky, Nimrang, Taify pink, Taify white, SulTony, Pozdny VIRa, Khusainy Muscat, etc. To obtain grapes suitable for long-term storage, the following practices must be implemented and these conditions must be observed: stop watering 10-15 days before harvesting, harvest grapes only in dry weather, during the hours when the dew has dried on the berries, and no earlier than 2-3 days after rain, carry out selective collection of well-ripened, healthy, loose bunches.

Grape bunches should be harvested carefully so as not to disturb the integrity of the bloom. At the processing of the bunches during selection, small, under-ripened, dried, damaged berries should be removed. It is not recommended to store unripe bunches and the berries of which are very densely and unevenly distributed along the cluster.

The ripeness of grapes can be determined organoleptically; the content of soluble solids according to a refractometer should be 18-22%, and the ratio of sugar to acid should be 18-20 units. These indicators vary depending on the grape variety and growing area.

The contents of each box should be uniform to facilitate storage control. Do not compress the bunches too much in the packages. Grape bunches should be placed in a cool room immediately after harvesting. Before this, the grapes should be kept in a dark place to avoid direct sunlight, but not more than 24 hours. It is advisable to precool grapes after harvesting.

During the entire storage period, it is necessary to maintain the optimal air temperature $+1, +2^{\circ}$ for these purposes and relative air humidity of 85-95%. When the humidity is less than 85% after long-term storage, the grape bunches dry out and the berries wilt.

The most effective method of storing grapes is using tableted potassium metabisulfite. For each box (7-8 kg) of grapes, 40-45 tablets are used. From a hygienic point of view, it is advisable to place tablets in perforated paper. When we use potassium metabisulfate, the shelf life is extended by 3-4 months, and the amount of waste is reduced by three to four times.

After filling the facility with grapes, short-term fumigation is carried out every 2 weeks, burning sulfur at the rate of 30 g/m^3 of the room. Sulfur dioxide is left in contact with the grapes for 40-50 minutes and then removed by ventilation. Stronger concentrations, frequent and prolonged use of fumigation of sulfur can cause harm to grapes (discoloration of berries and the appearance of an off-flavor).

When storing grapes, traditional methods are widely used. In the Tashkent region, one of the widely used method of storage is in "chiya" (reed braid) is widely used. To do this, use adobe, well-ventilated building with an exhaust pipe and windows, two or three holes at the base of the wall (vent) for a constant flow of air. Reed braids are installed along the walls in three or four tiers. In the third decade of September or October, the grapes are harvested and on the same day, after a thorough inspection, removing damaged, under-ripened and diseased berries, they are carefully placed in braids in one row with the peduncles up. In this way, all tiers are filled. The capacity of such storage is on average 1.0-1.5 tons.

After laying the grapes, the room is fumigated with sulfur dioxide at the rate of 30 g/m^3 of the room for 45-60 minutes, and then the facility is ventilated. During storage, products are inspected every 15-20 days and damaged bunches or berries are removed. This method can be used to store grapes until February-March. At the end of storage, the berries may wrinkle slightly, but retain their taste.

The "otan" method is widespread in the Fergana region, but is also common in the Tashkent region too. The building and the roof of the storage room are made of adobe; the ceilings have beams with a distance between them of 60-70 cm. The length of the room is 5 m, width is 3 m. For air circulation, two holes measuring 90x90 cm were made on one side of the wall, and one on the other. There is an exhaust pipe in the middle of the ceiling. There are two vents measuring 20x20 cm under the walls on both sides. Before placing the grapes, the room is fumigated with sulfur dioxide at the rate of $50-60 \text{ g/m}^3$ and ventilated after 1-2 days.

After harvesting, the grapes are left for 3-4 days to dry the cluster stem. At this time, "zang" is prepared, i.e. grapevines after pruning, the length of which depends on the height of the room. After the cluster stem have dried, the grapes are carefully sorted and good bunches are selected, which are tied like garlands on the "zang" closely. Tying of bunches starts from the bottom up. In this way, 35-40 kg grapes are tied in one "zang". The finished "zang" are hung on beams at a distance of 35-40 cm. After storing the grapes, the room is fumigated with sulfur at the rate of 30 g/m^3 for 60-80 minutes, after which it is ventilated. In this way, the grapes are stored until April.

The primary factors ensuring long-term storage of grapes are the correct choice of grape variety, timely and high-quality harvesting of grapes, ensuring the integrity of the berries when storing, accurate and timely adherence to storage conditions

Methods of the research

The storage of grapes has been carried out in conventional facility by using common methods:

Option I – hanging bunches of grapes in pairs on special frames.

Option II – tying bunches of grapes using “zang” method (Otan method) with a load of 35-40 kg on each vine.

Option III – the same method with a load of 15-20 kg per vine.

Option IV – laying bunches of grapes on tiers with spread on reed braids (“chiya”)

Option V – the same storage method (on tiers), but instead of braid, “chipta” burlap is used for laying bunches of grapes.

The results of research

The average daily air temperature during the storage period (see Table 1) ranged from +2,6 to 20,3°C, maximum 25°C, minimum -20°C, relative air humidity was 53,2-87,2%.

During the initial storage period (September) there was high temperature and low relative humidity, and in the final storage period (March-April) the temperature was also high, which negatively affected the quality and duration of storage of grapes.

Table- 1. Meteorological indicators at storage period

Meteorological indicators at the storage period of fresh grapes Storage period months	In the facility (monthly average)					
	Air temperature °C			Relative air humidity, %		
September	20,3			56,7		
October	12,8			79,0		
November	7,5			82,9		
December	5,4			85,3		
January	2,6			87,2		
February	3,7			85,0		
March	10,0			71,2		
April	17,1			53,2		
	Time measuring unit (hours)					
	9 a.m		1 p.m		5 p.m	
	Air temperature, °C	Relative air humidity, %	Air temperature, °C	Relative air humidity, %	Air temperature, °C	Relative air humidity, %
September	17,4	66,0	22,2	50,8	21,1	53,5
October	12	80,2	13,1	78,3	13,4	79,2
November	7	82,9	7,6	83,4	7,9	81,6
December	4,7	86	5,4	84,7	5,8	85,2
January	2	87,9	2,5	86,8	2,9	87,0
February	3,2	85,1	3,7	85,0	4,1	85
March	8,9	74	10,2	68,9	11	70,9
April	15,5	56,2	18,9	49,1	17	54,1

Figure 1 shows the average temperature and relative humidity at 9 a.m, 1 p.m, 5 p.m during the storage period. In the morning hours, the temperature was relatively low, the air humidity was high, and in the afternoon and evening hours the air temperature increased with low air humidity.

Figure- 1. Meteorological indicators at the storage of grapes.

The results of the study showed that the Kishmish white and Kishmish Khishrau grape varieties which were harvested earlier, began to quickly deteriorate and dry out during the storage. In this regard, all options of the experiment were removed from storage after 2 months, the yield of raw materials after storage was 55-71%, weight loss (drying) during the storage period was 23-33% (see Fig. 2 and Table 2).

Figure-2. Technological indicators of fresh grapes at the storage period.

Table- 2. Main technological parameters of fresh grapes at the storage period

Varieties and options	Sugariness %		Humidity, %		Duration of storage, days	Raw material yield after storage, %	Waste, %	Weight loss at storing, %
	before	after	before	after				
white Kishmish standard								
I	20,5	44,0	79,5	38,7	61	61,0	6,0	33,0
II	21,8	47,0	79,6	42,0	61	57,6	10,5	31,8
III	21,8	46,0	79,6	38,9	61	62,2	7,7	30,2
IV	21,8	47,0	79,6	49,2	61	62,2	8,2	27,7

V	21,6	45,0	79,6	50,0	61	64,8	8,7	26,5
Kishmish Khishrau								
I	21,0	39,5	77,6	49,7	61	65,0	4,0	31,0
II	20,5	37,0	77,7	50,7	61	55,0	15,0	30,0
III	21,6	40,5	77,6	49,5	61	65,0	7,0	28,0
IV	21,2	39,0	77,6	51,3	61	70,0	5,0	25,0
V	21,0	40,0	77,8	52,0	61	70,0	6,0	23,0

Grapes (Kishmish white, Kishmish Khishrau, Kishmish Botir, Taify pink, Khusayny Muscat, Khusayny) of late ripening and harvesting (1st decade of October) were stored longer and received positive ratings.

Mechanical analysis of raw materials showed that there were no significant differences in weight, volume, and dimensions when stored between the options. There were differences between varieties, which were determined by the varietal characteristics.

After removing the raw materials from storage, in all variants of the experiment, the mechanical analysis indicators were lower, which is a consequence of the drying of the raw materials during the storage period (see Table 3).

Table- 3. Storage duration, raw material yield and mechanical content of fresh grapes at the storage

Varieties and options	Storage duration, days	Raw material yield after storage, %
White Kishmish standard		
I	150	82,0
II	140,0	80,3
III	150,0	81,0
IV	150,0	81,5
V	150,0	81,0
I	150	82,0
Kishmish Khishrau		
I	150,0	77,8
II	150,0	77,0
III	150,0	77,3
IV	150,0	79,3
V	150,0	79,2
I	150,0	77,8
Khusayny Muscat		
I	150,0	79,8
II	150,0	79,5
III	150,0	81,5
IV	150,0	80,7
V	150,0	80,7
Khusayny standard		
I	150,0	80,5
II	150,0	79,0
III	150,0	81,2
IV	150,0	82,2
V	150,0	82,3
Kishmish Botir		
I	150,0	80,3

II	150,0		78,8					
III	150,0		80,3					
IV	150,0		80,5					
V	150,0		80,7					
Taify pink								
I	180,0		82,3					
II	180,0		81,4					
III	191,0		82,2					
IV	191,0		82,5					
V	191,0		82,5					
Varieties and options	Mechanical content of 100 berries							
	weight, g		length, cm		width, cm		volume, cm ³	
	before	after	before	after	before	after	before	after
White Kishmish standard								
I	143	65	130	96	116	70	135	58
II	145	70	135	98	120	68	138	61
III	145	66	135	96	120	68	138	58
IV	145	75	135	100	120	73	139	64
V	145	74	135	100	120	73	139	65
Khishmish Khishrau								
I	310	166	230	140	145	90	298	158
II	310	164	228	135	142	85	300	153
III	312	166	230	140	145	85	303	158
IV	312	170	230	143	145	90	300	160
V	310	173	230	145	145	92	300	165

In practice and according to literature data, it is usually recommended to store grapes by the end of September or early October. This is confirmed by our observations too. So, the grapes (white Kishmish, Kishmish Khishrau) of early ripening and harvesting (the first decade of September) were stored for up to 2 months, the grapes (white Kishmish, Taify pink, etc.) of late ripening and harvesting (the first decade of October) were stored for up to 5-6 months. The storage duration of fresh grapes, depending on the variety and experimental options, ranges from 140 to 191 days (see Table 3).

Grapes of the Taify pink variety were stored longer (191 days) when the bunches were tied on the vine with a load of 15-20 kg and when laying bunches on reed berdans and in “chiptu” on special tiers; shorter shelf life (140 days) was observed for white Kishmish variety when bunches were tied per vine with a load of 35-40 kg. This is due to the varietal characteristics.

The yield of raw materials after storage, depending on the variety and experimental options, ranged from 77,0 to 82,5%. In terms of the yield of raw materials, there are no significant differences among the experimental variants; but there is a difference between varieties. The varieties Kishmish white, Khuseyny and Taify pink were distinguished by a relatively high yield of raw materials (after storage) (see Table 2). A high yield (82,5%) was obtained with variants when tying bunches on the vine with a load of 15-20 kg, when laying bunches on reed braids and in “chipta”, i.e. in sackcloth of all grape varieties.

A relatively lower yield (77,0%) was obtained from Kishmish Khishrau variety when bunches were tied to the vine with a load of 35-40 kg. The decrease in yield was affected by weight loss and rotting of berries during storage, since the share (16,8%) of waste was higher than in other options.

Depending on the variety and experimental options, weight loss during the storage period ranges from 3,2 to 7,3%.

The smallest loss of weight 3,2-3,5% was noted in the option with laying bunches on “chipta” and on reed

braids in the Taify pink variety; therefore, in these options the quality indicators were higher. A large loss (drying of raw materials by 7,1-7,3%) of weight was observed in the variant with hanging bunches in pairs in the varieties Kishmish Khishrau and white Kishmish. And this, in turn, led to a decrease in the marketability of raw materials.

The highest drying results of raw materials were observed in all varieties when hanging bunches on a “chipta”.

Table- 4. Main technological parameters of fresh grapes at the storage period

Varieties and options	sugariness, %		humidity, %		Storage duration, days	Yield of raw material after storage %	Waste, % before	Weight loss at storing, g
	At the storage							
	before	after	before	after				
White Kishmish standard								
I	23,2	36,0	79,0	58,1	150	82,0	10,7	7,3
II	23,0	34,5	79,0	60,0	140	80,3	13,3	6,2
III	23,0	36,0	79,0	62,8	150	81,0	12,0	7,0
IV	23,2	35,5	79,0	66,6	150	81,5	13,8	4,7
V	23,2	35,0	79,0	67,5	150	81,0	15,2	3,8
Kishmish Khishrau								
I	22,5	36,0	77,0	62,2	150	77,8	15,1	7,1
II	22,2	34,5	77,0	66,1	150	77,0	16,8	6,2
III	22,2	35,0	77,0	62,1	150	77,3	16,0	6,2
IV	22,5	37,0	77,0	66,6	150	79,3	15,7	5,0
V	22,4	35,5	77,0	67,0	150	79,2	16,5	4,3
Khusayny Muscat								
I	19,0	28,0	82,0	69,5	150	79,8	15,3	4,8
II	19,0	27,5	82,5	70,1	150	79,5	16,3	4,2
III	18,5	25,5	82,5	71,6	150	81,5	13,8	4,7
IV	19,2	30,0	83,0	74,6	150	80,7	15,3	4,0
V	19,0	28,5	83,0	75,0	150	80,7	15,4	3,9
Khusayny standard								
I	19,0	24,5	80,2	71,3	160	80,5	13,7	5,8
II	19,0	25,0	80,2	73,2	150	79,0	16,3	4,7
III	19,5	35,0	80,0	72,2	150	81,2	13,3	5,5
IV	19,5	30,0	80,2	74,5	150	82,2	13,7	4,2
V	19,5	34,5	80,2	75,3	150	82,3	14,0	3,6
Khishmish Botir								
I	23,0	29,0	79,5	67,5	150	80,3	13,3	6,3
II	23,5	27,0	79,5	72,5	150	78,8	16,0	5,2
III	23,0	27,0	79,5	69,5	150	80,3	13,7	6,0
IV	23,5	28,0	79,8	74,0	150	80,5	14,8	4,5
V	23,5	28,5	79,5	74,8	150	80,7	15,3	4,0
Taify pink								
I	17,5	22,7	83,0	73,2	180	82,3	12,9	4,8
II	17,5	22,0	82,8	74,4	180	81,4	14,6	4,0
III	18,0	23,6	82,8	73,8	191	82,2	13,5	4,3
IV	18,0	23,0	82,5	75,0	191	82,5	14,0	3,5
V	18,0	23,0	82,5	75,6	191	82,5	14,3	3,2

The organoleptic assessment of fresh grapes after storage for the tested varieties is in the range of 7,0-8,65 points.

During the storage period for the varieties white Kishmish and Kishmish Khishrau, degustation was conducted twice on January 15 and March 1. The varieties white Kishmish and Kishmish Khishrau received a good score in January (8,05-8,55 points), in March they received a relatively low score (7,2-7,8 points) among all variants of the experiment.

From the abovementioned, it is clear that the most optimal storage period for the varieties white Kishmish and Kishmish Khishrau is until the second decade of January (see Table 4). In the varieties Taify pink and Kishmish Botir, the placement of bunches on reed braids and in “chipta” stands out with a good organoleptic assessment (8.25-8.55 points), and the Khusayny variety received a relatively low score (7,0-7,2 points) among all options of experiment. The reason for the decrease in quality indicators for the Khusayny variety was a drop in temperature to minus 2°C in January-February indoors.

Based on the results of storing fresh grapes white Kishmish, Kishmish Khishrau, Taify pink, Khusainy Muscat, Khuseyny, Kishmish Botir for the period from September to April 10, the following preliminary conclusions can be drawn.

During the storage period (September-April), the average daily air temperature ranged from +2,6 to 20,3°C, maximum 25°C, minimum -2°C, and relative air humidity was 53,2-87,2% . A decrease in the temperature in the room below -2°C negatively affects quality indicators and worsens the presentation and marketability of raw materials.

The duration of the storage of fresh grapes by variety ranges from 61 to 191 days.

Early storage (the first ten days of September) of early ripening grape varieties white Kishmish, Kishmish Khishrau reduces the storage duration due to increased temperature and low relative humidity in the room.

Grapes in the experimented varieties of a later ripening date (1st decade of October) were stored from 140 to 191 days. Taify pink was stored longer (191 days) when bunches were tied to vines with a load of 15-20 kg when laid on reed braids. White Kishmish variety were stored less (140 days) when bunches were tied to the vine with a load of 35-40 kg.

A relatively high yield (77,3-82,5%) was obtained for all grape varieties when bunches were tied to the vine with a load of 15-20 kg when the bunches were laid on reed braids and in “chipta”.

Of the tested varieties, Taify pink grape variety stands out in terms of yield when laying bunches on reed braids and in “chipta” (82,5%). Kishmish Khishrau has a relatively lower yield of 77% when tying bunches to a vine with a load of 35-40 kg.

A good organoleptic assessment (8,25-8,65 points) was found in the options Taify pink and Kishmish Botir varieties when laying bunches on reed braids and in the “chipta”. The Khusayny variety received a low score (7,0-7,2 points) in all variants of the experiment.

Thus, it was concluded by the research results that the new varieties Kishmish Khishrau and Khusayny Muscat (medium-late ripening, harvesting in early October) after 150 days, i.e., by February had good taste quality and a high yield of raw materials after storage.

References:

1. Magomedov. M.G. Basics of storage technology. Book – Russia, 2015
2. Gorlov S.M., Tyagusheva A.A., Yasushko, Karpenko E.N.-Journal. Kuban State Agrarian University. Russia, 2020.
3. Yasushko E.S. Technology of storage of table varieties of grape - Dissertation. Russia, 2021.
4. Smirnov K.V., Radjabov A.S., Morozova G.S. - Workshop on viticulture. – Moscow, “Kolos”, 1995.
5. Dzheneev S.Yu. Storage of table grapes on farms. – Moscow, “Kolos”, 1978.